

ASSESSING THE IMPACT OF GABRIELIAN-CARE: STUDENT PERCEPTIONS, EFFECTIVENESS, AND BARRIERS TO HELP-SEEKING BEHAVIOR AT COLEGIO DE SAN GABRIEL ARCANGEL

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ABSTRACT

This study explores the influence of Gabrielian-Care, the flagship mental health and wellness program of Colegio de San Gabriel Arcangel, by examining student perceptions, its perceived effectiveness, and barriers to help-seeking. Anchored in the Gabrielian philosophy, "Vir Enim Dei – Man of God," and rooted in the values of psychological discipline, righteous transformation, and selfless service, the research adopts a mixed-methods approach. Quantitative surveys and qualitative focus group discussions were conducted with selected students. Findings indicate that students generally view Gabrielian-Care as a values-based initiative fostering emotional well-being and compassionate campus culture. However, the program's full potential is hindered by persistent stigma, fear of judgment, limited mental health awareness, and cultural reluctance to seek support. Despite these barriers, students recognize its role in enhancing resilience, building meaningful connections, and nurturing an inclusive environment grounded in empathy. The study underscores the need to strengthen mental health advocacy, expand support systems, and implement culturally responsive strategies to normalize help-seeking. Gabrielian-Care is ultimately seen not only as a response to student mental health needs but also as a living expression of the institution's mission: "To transform oneself righteously and selflessly serve others with a caring heart."

Keywords: *gabrielian-care, mental health, student perceptions, help seeking behavior, psychosocial support.*

INTRODUCTION

Gabrielian-Care, formerly known as POBLA-CARE, is a psychosocial support program at Colegio de San Gabriel Arcangel (CDSGA) designed to address the emotional and academic challenges students encounter, particularly in the post-pandemic environment. The program aims to foster a proactive help-seeking attitude among students by providing structured activities that promote emotional resilience, self-awareness, and the ability to seek help when needed. Gabrielian-Care focuses on supporting students through their academic and personal challenges while preparing them for transitions to higher education or the workforce. By creating a safe and supportive space, the program encourages students to break the stigma around seeking help, ultimately developing their skills to navigate future difficulties with confidence. This initiative, facilitated by teachers and school coordinator, has evolved to meet the growing needs of students, especially in their senior high school years, helping them develop strong support systems that will last beyond their time in school.

In recent years, mental health has emerged as a critical concern within higher education, with increasing numbers of college students facing psychological challenges such as stress, anxiety, depression, and emotional exhaustion. While this trend reflects a global pattern, it is especially pressing in the Philippine context, where access to mental health services remains uneven and often hindered by deep-rooted stigma, financial constraints, and limited institutional support. Although the passage of the Mental Health Act of 2018 (RA 11036) was a significant step toward mental health awareness and care, many students continue to struggle in silence due to cultural apprehensions, lack of awareness, and fear of judgment.

Recognizing these challenges, Colegio de San Gabriel Arcangel (CDSGA) launched Gabrielian-Care, a comprehensive mental health and psychosocial support initiative. This program is rooted in the institution's core values and Gabrielian identity—emphasizing psychological discipline, selfless service, and the moral transformation of individuals. It aligns with the school's guiding philosophy: "To transform one's self-righteously and selflessly serve others with a caring heart." Gabrielian-Care offers a range of services including counseling, mental health education, peer support initiatives, and wellness campaigns—all designed to promote emotional well-being and holistic development among students.

Despite the program's strong foundation and vision, its actual reach, effectiveness, and impact from the students' perspective have yet to be systematically evaluated. While informal feedback suggests positive impressions, recurring concerns such as fear of stigma, uncertainty about confidentiality, and limited understanding of mental health services continue to deter students from seeking help. These barriers not only undermine the program's goals but also highlight the need for a deeper understanding of students' experiences and attitudes toward mental health support.

The study titled "Assessing the Impact of Gabrielian-Care: Student Perceptions, Effectiveness, and Barriers to Help-Seeking Behavior at Colegio de San Gabriel Arcangel" seeks to evaluate the impact of this psychosocial support program through

student perceptions, its overall effectiveness, and the barriers students encounter when seeking help. The study is structured to address several key questions: First, it will examine the demographic profile of the respondents, including factors such as Junior High School Origin, Gender Identity, and Senior High School Level. The study will then assess how students evaluate Gabrielian-Care based on the following categories: awareness and accessibility, trust and confidentiality, effectiveness of services, influence on help-seeking behavior, perceived barriers to using the program, and student satisfaction with the program, along with any recommendations they may have. Additionally, the study will explore whether there are significant differences in assessments based on demographic factors, allowing for an analysis of how these variables impact student perceptions and experiences with the program. Finally, the study will offer recommendations for feasible programs or interventions to improve and strengthen the services provided by Gabrielian-Care, ensuring it continues to meet the evolving needs of the students at CDSGA.

This research aims to address the gap in understanding the true impact of Gabrielian-Care by grounding its inquiry in the lived experiences of the students. Through this, the study hopes to provide meaningful insights that will strengthen the program and foster a more empathetic, responsive, and stigma-free mental health culture at CDSGA. Ultimately, the study contributes to both institutional improvement and broader academic discourse, aligning with CDSGA's mission to develop psychologically disciplined, socially responsible, and functionally productive individuals. The findings will offer valuable implications for mental health programming in other faith-based and service-driven educational institutions across the Philippines.

The increasing prevalence of mental health issues among college students has become a global concern. Studies show that academic pressure, social isolation, financial stress, and uncertainty about the future significantly impact students' psychological well-being (Auerbach et al., 2016; WHO, 2021). In the Philippines, recent data indicate that depression and anxiety are among the most common mental health concerns affecting youth and young adults. Educational institutions are now being challenged to go beyond traditional academic roles by fostering emotionally supportive learning environments.

In response, universities are establishing wellness programs to address the growing need for psychological support. However, the presence of services does not guarantee utilization. There is often a disparity between the availability of mental health programs and the actual number of students who access them (Eisenberg, et.al., 2012).

Help-seeking behavior refers to the process through which individuals seek support from professional or informal sources for psychological distress. According to Rickwood, et.al., (2005), help-seeking is influenced by several personal and social factors, including the recognition of mental health symptoms, belief in the effectiveness of counseling, and confidence in the confidentiality of services.

In school settings, students often prefer to confide in peers or family members rather than seek professional counseling (Gulliver, et.al., 2010). Although mental health programs like Gabrielian-Care are designed to support students, their effectiveness

hinges on students' willingness to utilize them. Understanding what encourages or discourages this behavior is essential in program evaluation and redesign.

Several studies have identified consistent barriers to help-seeking in both Western and Asian contexts. These include stigma, fear of judgment, lack of awareness, low mental health literacy, and misconceptions about counseling (Corrigan, 2004). In Filipino culture, where family reputation (*hiya*) and resilience (*tiis*) are deeply embedded, seeking psychological help is often misinterpreted as a sign of weakness.

Even in academic settings that promote inclusivity and mental health awareness, internalized stigma and cultural values may discourage students from using available services (Martinez et al., 2020). For faith-based institutions like CDSGA, there is a unique opportunity to reframe help-seeking as a responsible, righteous, and caring act aligned with Christian and Gabrielian values.

Mental health programs must be both accessible and culturally relevant to be effective. According to Sue and Sue (2016), culturally responsive interventions recognize the influence of language, spirituality, family systems, and social values on students' mental health experiences. In the Philippine setting, community-based and values-driven approaches have shown greater acceptance, particularly when interventions are framed within the context of service, spirituality, and shared responsibility.

Gabrielian-Care, as part of Colegio De San Gabriel Arcangel's commitment to holistic student formation, stands as a prime example of an institutionally anchored mental health support system. Its alignment with the school's core principles of psychological discipline, interdependence, and selfless care makes it uniquely positioned to meet both the academic and emotional needs of its students. However, a systematic evaluation is required to determine its actual effectiveness, levels of student engagement, and the obstacles that hinder help-seeking—thus affirming the research ability of this present study.

While a growing body of literature emphasizes the importance of mental health programs in universities, there remains a significant gap in localized and context-specific assessments. Most studies focus on general barriers or psychological profiles without evaluating program-specific outcomes. At Colegio De San Gabriel Arcangel, Gabrielian-Care presents a unique model rooted in transformational, service-oriented education. Yet, there is limited empirical data on its perceived effectiveness, student reception, and the cultural or institutional barriers that may affect its utilization. Addressing this gap is essential in strengthening the program and advancing mental health advocacy aligned with Gabrielian values.

Ma et al. (2022) conducted a systematic review to evaluate the effectiveness of school-based interventions designed to enhance mental health literacy and reduce stigma among children and adolescents aged 4 to 18 years. The findings provide moderate evidence that such interventions are effective in improving mental health literacy and reducing stigma associated with mental disorders. However, the review also notes limited evidence regarding their long-term effectiveness, primarily due to a lack of follow-up

studies. Additionally, the authors highlight significant methodological heterogeneity among the studies reviewed and emphasize the need for future research to incorporate outcome assessments and process evaluations to enhance the design and implementation of school-based mental health interventions.

O'Farrell, et.al.,(2022) conducted a systematic review focusing on the assessment of mental health in schools and teachers' perceptions of their role in identifying and supporting students with mental health difficulties. The review emphasizes the crucial role of teachers as frontline gatekeepers, considering the substantial amount of time children spend in school and the importance of early identification and intervention for mental health issues. Unlike previous reviews that primarily focused on interventions, this study addresses a gap in the literature by examining mental health assessment practices within school settings and their implications for educational policy.

Key findings revealed that teachers encounter significant barriers, including insufficient training in mental health assessment and role conflict, largely due to limited knowledge, skills, and confidence in addressing mental health concerns. The review underscores the need for comprehensive and sustained mental health training—both during pre-service education and through ongoing professional development—to better equip teachers in supporting students' psychological well-being.

Priestley et al. (2022) conducted a study exploring student perspectives on enhancing mental health services at UK universities through co-creation panels. These panels generated rich qualitative data, from which three overarching themes emerged: mental health services, mental health culture, and university culture and environment. This particular paper focused on the theme of mental health services, emphasizing students' recommendations for improving the accessibility and effectiveness of embedded university support systems.

Students advocated for a proactive and preventative approach to mental health, highlighting the importance of early identification, supportive staff-student relationships, and the cultivation of a caring institutional culture. Rather than proposing entirely new services, they called for a more strategic, coordinated, and inclusive approach to service delivery that responds to the diverse needs of the student body. Identified barriers included long wait times, inconvenient service locations, limited awareness of available resources, and persistent stigma surrounding mental health.

Additionally, students stressed the significance of strong leadership, cohesive policy frameworks, and data-informed decision-making to enhance service coordination and resource allocation. The findings align with the principles of the University Mental Health Charter, reinforcing the value of a whole-university approach to promoting student mental health and well-being.

Lui et al. (2022) conducted a systematic review investigating the experiences of university students with common mental disorders, particularly depression and anxiety. The study aimed to identify key barriers and facilitators to help-seeking behavior among this population, with the goal of informing improvements in mental health service delivery

within higher education. A comprehensive search was conducted across EMBASE, MEDLINE, and PsycINFO for studies published between 1990 and 2021, written in English, and employing either qualitative or quantitative methodologies.

To be included, studies had to involve university students diagnosed with depression or anxiety, explicitly examine help-seeking barriers and facilitators, and report a sample in which more than 60% of participants had a diagnosed mental illness. A total of ten studies met the inclusion criteria. The most commonly reported barriers to help-seeking were high levels of self-reliance, perceived stigma, and low mental health literacy. In contrast, key facilitators included strong mental health literacy and social encouragement from peers, family, or faculty.

Research Questions

The main objective of this research was to assess the impact of Gabrielian-Care in terms of student perceptions, its effectiveness, and the barriers to help-seeking behavior at Colegio De San Gabriel Arcangel. Moreover, the study aimed to examine the relationship between demographic factors, such as Junior High School Origin, gender identity, and senior high school level, and the respondents' assessment of Gabrielian-Care's impact based on the variables.

Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the respondents of the study when they are grouped according to their demographic factors such as:
 - 1.1. Junior High School Origin,
 - 1.2. Gender Identity, and
 - 1.3. Senior High School Level?

2. How do the respondents assess the impact of Gabrielian-Care as a Psychosocial Support Program based on the following categories:
 - 2.1. Awareness and Accessibility of Gabrielian-Care;
 - 2.2. Trust and Confidentiality;
 - 2.3. Effectiveness of Gabrielian -Care Services;
 - 2.4. Influence on Help-Seeking Behavior.
 - 2.5. Perceived Barriers to Using Gabrielian -Care; and
 - 2.6. Student Satisfaction and Recommendations?

3. Are there significant differences in the respondents' assessment of the impact of Gabrielian -Care as a Psychosocial Support Program based on the following categories: Awareness and Accessibility of Gabrielian -Care, Trust and Confidentiality, Effectiveness of Gabrielian -Care Services, Influence on Help-Seeking Behavior, Perceived Barriers to Using Gabrielian -Care, and Student Satisfaction and Recommendations when grouped according to their demographic factors such as:
 - 3.1. Junior High School Origin,
 - 3.2. Gender Identity, and
 - 3.3. Senior High School Level?

4. In light of the study's findings, what feasible program or intervention can be proposed to improve and strengthen the services provided by Gabrielian -Care at Colegio De San Gabriel Arcangel?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study employed a mixed-methods research design to comprehensively assess the impact of the Gabrielian-Care program on students' help-seeking behavior at Colegio de San Gabriel Arcangel. The research design was structured in two distinct but interconnected phases: quantitative followed by qualitative.

Research Locale

This study was conducted at the first Extension Campus of Colegio de San Gabriel Arcangel (CDSGA), located in the Población of San Jose del Monte City, Bulacan. The population of this study included all Grade 11 and Grade 12 Senior High School (SHS) students enrolled at Colegio de San Gabriel Arcangel, Población Campus, during the Academic Year 2024–2025.

Data Gathering Process

The study gathered relevant data of the Student Perceptions, Effectiveness, and Barriers to Help-Seeking Behavior utilized both quantitative and qualitative instruments appropriate for a mixed-methods design. The data collection for the study titled "Assessing the Impact of Gabrielian-Care: Student Perceptions, Effectiveness, and Barriers to Help-Seeking Behavior at Colegio de San Gabriel Arcangel, Poblacion Campus, San Jose del Monte City, Bulacan" followed a two-phase process aligned with the study's mixed-methods explanatory sequential design. This research will cover the following areas: 1. It will evaluate three main variables: student perceptions, perceived effectiveness, and barriers to help-seeking, and how these relate to help-seeking behavior. 2. Both quantitative (via survey questionnaires) and qualitative (via focus group discussions) data will be collected to ensure a comprehensive understanding. 3. And it aims to propose data-driven recommendations to enhance the delivery and accessibility of Gabrielian-Care services. The delimitation of this research includes the following: 1. The study excludes students from basic education, college, and graduate school. 2. Mental health outcomes such as specific diagnoses, therapy outcomes, or long-term interventions will not be assessed. 3. The effectiveness of individual counselors or clinical methods will not be evaluated. 4. And the external mental health services outside of Gabrielian-Care are not part of this study.

Data Analysis

For Problem 1, Frequency and percentage were used to summarize and describe the demographic characteristics of the respondents, including Junior High School Origin, gender identity, grade level, and awareness of Gabrielian-Care. For Problem 2, To analyze students' assessments across the six key dimensions—Awareness and Accessibility, Trust and Confidentiality, Effectiveness of Services, Influence on Help-Seeking Behavior, Perceived Barriers, and Student Satisfaction—mean and standard deviation were computed to measure central tendency and variability in responses. For Problem 3, To determine whether perceptions and assessments varied significantly when grouped by Junior High School Origin, Gender Identity, and Senior High School Level, the study employed t-tests. All inferential analyses were conducted at a 0.05 level of significance ($p < 0.05$), indicating statistical significance if the likelihood of results occurring by chance was less than 5%.

These statistical treatments provided both descriptive and inferential insights, contributing to a data-driven understanding of how Gabrielian-Care was perceived and experienced by students.

RESULTS

This section presents the Results, Analysis, and Discussion of the study.

1. Profile of the respondents of the study.

Table 1. Junior High School Origin Profile of the Respondents.

Junior High School Origin	Frequency	Percentage
Private School	7	5.38
Public School	123	94.62

Table 2. Gender Identity Profile of the Respondents.

Junior High School Origin	Frequency	Percentage
Private School	7	5.38
Public School	123	94.62

Table 3. Senior High School Profile of the Respondents.

Senior High School Level	Frequency	Percentage
Grade 11	104	80.00
Grade 12	26	20.00

2. Summary on the respondent's assessment of the impact of Gabrielian-care as a psychosocial support program.

Table 4. Assessment of the Respondent on the impact of Gabrielian-care as a psychosocial support program.

Variables	Weighted mean	Descriptive Equivalent
Awareness and accessibility	3.21	High
Trust and Confidentiality	3.24	High
Effectiveness of Gabrielian-care	3.22	High
Influence on help-seeking behavior	3.11	High
Perceived barriers to using Gabrielian-care	2.27	Low
Student satisfaction and recommendation	3.29	Very High

3. Test of difference in the assessment of Gabrielian-care as a psychosocial support program

Table 5. T-Test and F-Test (ANOVA) Results on the Impact of Gabrielian-Care in terms of awareness and accessibility when respondents are grouped according to their demographic information.

Demographic Information	Sub-Groups	Mean	Ratio	Crit-Value	df	p-value	Decision when $\alpha = 0.05$
JHS Origin	Private	3.64	1.52	1.66	128	0.07	Accept
	Public	3.25					
Gender Identity	Female	3.34	1.17	1.66	128	0.12	Accept
	Male	3.20					
SHS Year Level	Grade 11	3.32	1.85	1.66	128	0.03	Reject
	Grade 12	3.03					

Table 6. T-Test and F-Test (ANOVA) Results on the Impact of Gabrielian-Care in terms of trust and confidentiality when respondents are grouped according to their demographic information.

Demographic Information	Sub-Groups	Mean	Ratio	Crit-Value	df	p-value	Decision when $\alpha = 0.05$
JHS Origin	Private	3.26	0.08	1.66	128	0.47	Accept
	Public	3.23					
Gender Identity	Female	3.32	1.38	1.66	128	0.08	Accept
	Male	3.14					
SHS Year Level	Grade 11	3.23	0.43	1.66	128	0.33	Accept
	Grade 12	3.15					

Table 7. T-Test and F-Test (ANOVA) Results on the Impact of Gabrielian-Care in terms of effectiveness when respondents are grouped according to their demographic information.

Demographic Information	Sub-Groups	Mean	Ratio	Crit-Value	df	p-value	Decision when $\alpha = 0.05$
JHS Origin	Private	3.26	0.13	1.66	128	0.45	Accept
	Public	3.22					
Gender Identity	Female	3.32	1.77	1.66	128	0.04	Reject
	Male	3.10					
SHS Year Level	Grade 11	3.20	0.34	1.66	128	0.37	Accept
	Grade 12	3.26					

Table 8. T-Test and F-Test (ANOVA) Results on the Impact of Gabrielian-Care in terms of influence when respondents are grouped according to their demographic information.

Demographic Information	Sub-Groups	Mean	Ratio	Crit-Value	df	p-value	Decision when $\alpha = 0.05$
JHS Origin	Private	3.20	0.30	1.66	128	0.38	Accept
	Public	3.11					
Gender Identity	Female	3.20	1.33	1.66	128	0.09	Accept
	Male	3.01					
SHS Year Level	Grade 11	3.10	0.15	1.66	128	0.44	Accept
	Grade 12	3.13					

Table 8. T-Test and F-Test (ANOVA) Results on the Impact of Gabrielian-Care in terms of influence when respondents are grouped according to their demographic information.

Demographic Information	Sub-Groups	Mean	Ratio	Crit-Value	df	p-value	Decision when $\alpha = 0.05$
JHS Origin	Private	2.40	0.45	1.66	128	0.33	Accept
	Public	2.26					
Gender Identity	Female	2.30	0.39	1.66	128	0.35	Accept
	Male	2.24					
SHS Year Level	Grade 11	2.30	0.98	1.66	128	0.16	Accept
	Grade 12	2.10					

Table 9. T-Test and F-Test (ANOVA) Results on the Impact of Gabrielian-Care in terms of student satisfaction when respondents are grouped according to their demographic information.

Demographic Information	Sub-Groups	Mean	Ratio	Crit-Value	df	p-value	Decision when $\alpha = 0.05$
JHS Origin	Private	3.51	0.89	1.66	128	0.19	Accept
	Public	3.28					
Gender Identity	Female	3.38	1.71	1.66	128	0.05	Accept
	Male	3.18					
SHS Year Level	Grade 11	3.29	0.42	1.66	128	0.34	Accept
	Grade 12	3.22					

Figure 1. Paradigm of Gabrielian-care – V.O.I.C.E

Table 10. Proposed Program for Gabrielian-care “V.O.I.C.E – Validate, Open-up, Include, Connect, Empower”.

Activities	
Targeted Support Initiatives	Expansion of Program Integration
Gender-Sensitive Programming	Mental Health Orientation and Peer Campaigns
Grade 11 Mental Health Orientation	Thematic Group Support
Improved Visibility Campaigns	Private Counselling and Drop
Trust-Building Activities	Mental Wellness Workshops
Regular Feedback and Evaluation	First Respondent Peer Network Program

Gender-Responsive Interventions	Gabrielian-Care Room Enhancement Initiative
Stigma-Reduction Strategies	Facilitator training
Feedback Mechanisms	

DISCUSSION

1. Demographic profile of the respondents

Table 1.1 illustrates the junior high school origin of the student-respondents from Senior High School Department of Colegio de San Gabriel Arcangel, Inc. The data indicate that the vast majority of respondents graduated from public schools, accounting for 94.62% (n = 123) of the total population. In contrast, only a small portion of the respondents, 5.38% (n = 7), came from private schools. This suggests that most students enrolled in the institution have a public-school background, which may reflect broader trends in accessibility and affordability of education in the local context. Table 1.2 presents the gender identity distribution of the student-respondents from Colegio de San Gabriel Arcangel, Inc. The data reveal that the majority of the respondents identify as female, comprising 54.62% (n = 71) of the total population. Meanwhile, 45.38% (n = 59) identify as male. This slight predominance of female respondents suggests a relatively balanced gender representation among the participants, with a modest female majority. Table 1.3 illustrates the distribution of the respondents based on their Senior High School level. The data show that the majority of respondents are Grade 11 students, representing 80.00% (n = 104) of the total sample. In contrast, Grade 12 students make up 20.00% (n = 26) of the respondents. This significant proportion of Grade 11 students suggests that the study predominantly reflects the experiences and perceptions of students who are in their initial year of Senior High School.

2. Assessment of the respondents on the impact of Gabrielian-care as a psychosocial support program.

Students generally found the program accessible and well-promoted, though they recommended more straightforward guidelines and improved access processes. While most students trust the program's ability to maintain confidentiality, some remain hesitant to share personal concerns, highlighting the need for continued reassurance. Gabrielian-Care is widely regarded as effective in promoting emotional well-being, though responses vary, indicating room for more consistent and tailored services. The program successfully encourages help-seeking and reduces hesitation, fostering a supportive environment for mental health. Barriers to accessing services are minimal, reflecting its positive reception and accessibility. Overall, students expressed high satisfaction and a strong willingness to recommend the program, suggesting its effectiveness and value while emphasizing the importance of increased visibility and integration.

3. Test of difference in the assessment of Gabrielian-care as a psychosocial support program

A significant difference was found in Senior High School Year Level with a p-value = 0.03 (< 0.05), thus the null hypothesis is rejected. This means that there is a statistically significant difference in the respondents' assessment of the awareness and accessibility of Gabrielian-Care based on their year level. It is interpreted that Grade 11 students (Mean = 3.32) rated awareness and accessibility of the program higher compared to Grade 12 students (Mean = 3.03).

No significant differences were found in the student-respondents' assessment of trust and confidentiality in the Gabrielian-Care program when grouped according to their Junior High School (JHS) origin, gender identity, and Senior High School (SHS) year level. This suggests that these demographic factors do not significantly influence students' perceptions of the program's ability to maintain confidentiality and build trust.

No significant differences were found in the student-respondents' assessment of trust and confidentiality in the Gabrielian-Care program when grouped according to their Junior High School (JHS) origin, gender identity, and Senior High School (SHS) year level. This suggests that these demographic factors do not significantly influence students' perceptions of the program's ability to maintain confidentiality and build trust. A significant difference was found based on gender identity with a p-value = 0.04 (< 0.05), prompting the rejection of the null hypothesis.

However, no significant differences were found in the assessment of Gabrielian-Care's service effectiveness based on Junior High School origin or SHS year level. The analysis revealed that no significant differences were found in the respondents' assessment of Gabrielian-Care's influence on help-seeking behavior when grouped according to Junior High School origin, gender identity, and SHS¹ year level. All p-values were greater than the 0.05 level of significance, indicating acceptance of the null hypothesis across all demographic categories. The results show that no statistically significant differences were found in the assessment of perceived barriers to using Gabrielian-Care across the demographic variables of JHS origin, gender identity, and SHS year level.

All p-values exceed the 0.05 significance level, leading to the acceptance of the null hypothesis in all cases. The analysis reveals no statistically significant differences in the student-respondents' assessment of satisfaction and recommendation of Gabrielian-Care when grouped according to JHS origin, gender identity, and SHS year level. All p-values are above the 0.05 threshold, leading to acceptance of the null hypothesis across all demographic factors.

The proposed enhancements to Gabrielian-Care involve a multi-faceted approach, beginning with the implementation of targeted support initiatives. These will include

differentiated orientation programs for students from public and private school backgrounds, integrating psychosocial components that address the distinct challenges of transitioning into senior high school. Early mental health education will be embedded in Grade 11 onboarding processes through seminars and peer mentor introductions.

Conclusions

1. Demographic profile of the respondents

Most student-respondents graduated from public schools. This suggests the need for Gabrielian-Care to consider diverse educational backgrounds, especially those with limited prior access to psychosocial support. Respondents were fairly gender-balanced, with a slight female majority. This implies that gender considerations should remain central in program planning. A greater number of respondents were from Grade 11. Thus, initial-year experiences are crucial in shaping perceptions of support services.

2. Assessment of the respondents on the impact of Gabrielian-care as a psychosocial support program.

Students generally found the program accessible and well-promoted, though improvements in clarity and access processes are recommended. Students trust the program to maintain confidentiality, though some remain hesitant to share personal concerns, indicating the need for continued reassurance. Gabrielian-Care is viewed as effective in promoting emotional well-being, though responses vary, suggesting opportunities for more consistent and tailored services. The program encourages help-seeking and reduces hesitation, fostering a supportive environment for mental health support. Barriers to accessing services are minimal, reflecting the program's positive reception and accessibility among students. High levels of satisfaction and strong willingness to recommend the program highlight its effectiveness and value, with students suggesting increased visibility and integration.

3. Test of difference in the assessment of Gabrielian-care as a psychosocial support program

Significant differences were found between SHS levels, with Grade 11 students reporting higher awareness. No significant differences were observed based on JHS origin or gender. No significant differences were found across all demographic groups, indicating consistent trust in the program. Only gender identity showed substantial differences, with female students perceiving the program as more effective, suggesting a need for gender-responsive strategies. No significant differences were noted, indicating consistent program impact across demographics. No significant differences were found, though early-year students and females showed slightly higher means, suggesting a need for early orientation reinforcement.

No significant differences emerged, reflecting the program's general acceptability and effectiveness across all student groups.

Recommendations

1. Demographic profile of the respondents

Develop tailored support initiatives that address the varying needs of students from both public and private school backgrounds, particularly enhancing orientation and psychosocial transition programs for those with limited prior access to mental health resources. Ensure gender-sensitive programming by incorporating diverse emotional expression strategies and inclusive language in mental health communication to engage all gender identities meaningfully. Strengthen mental health awareness and engagement efforts at the Grade 12 level by integrating Gabrielian-Care orientation into onboarding activities to maximize early exposure and program familiarity.

2. Assessment of the respondents on the impact of Gabrielian-care as a psychosocial support program.

Improve visibility by implementing targeted information campaigns, clear referral protocols, and accessible entry points, especially during the start of each academic year. Enhance trust-building measures by training staff in trauma-informed care, providing assurances of confidentiality, and promoting peer ambassador programs that normalize help-seeking behavior. Conduct regular feedback sessions and satisfaction surveys to identify service gaps and tailor program components to meet evolving student needs more consistently. Sustain and expand outreach programs that reduce stigma and normalize mental health support through classroom integration, social media, and mental health literacy activities. Although barriers are generally low, reinforce stigma-reduction efforts and provide culturally responsive strategies, especially for students exhibiting self-reliant tendencies or unfamiliarity with counseling norms. Maintain high service quality while expanding Gabrielian-Care's visibility through campus-wide activities, open forums, and collaboration with faculty and student organizations to further embed the program in school culture.

3. Test of difference in the assessment of Gabrielian-care as a psychosocial support program

Standardized access to orientation and information materials across year levels to ensure equal awareness among all students, including refresher activities for Grade 12 students. Continuing consistent, transparent practices and reinforce the confidentiality protocols through student-led testimonials and mental health workshops that build community trust. Design gender-responsive interventions, including safe spaces, male-focused mental health sessions, and inclusive messaging, to engage underrepresented or less responsive gender groups. Expand current programming to include peer mentorship, teacher-led encouragement, and anonymous consultation options to maintain the inclusive impact of the program. Introduce additional orientation and stigma-reduction strategies at the beginning of SHS, particularly targeting Grade 11 students and female students who reported slightly higher perceived barriers. Continue consistent delivery while integrating ongoing feedback mechanisms such as focus groups or digital suggestion boxes to further adapt services to student needs.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

Participants signed separate informed consent forms for interviews. All discussions were audio-recorded with permission, transcribed verbatim, and securely stored. Identifiers were removed to protect participant confidentiality. Qualitative data were coded and thematically analyzed immediately following transcription. The integration of both quantitative and qualitative findings was performed during the interpretation phase. The researcher strictly adhered to ethical principles in conducting the study “Assessing the Impact of Gabrielian-Care: Student Perceptions, Effectiveness, and Barriers to Help-Seeking Behavior at Colegio de San Gabriel Arcangel, Poblacion Campus, San Jose del Monte City, Bulacan. Before the conduct of the study, approval was sought and obtained from the Research Ethics Committee of Colegio de San Gabriel Arcangel. The research design, instruments, and procedures were evaluated to ensure the study met established ethical standards.

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REFERENCES

- Auerbach, R. P., Alonso, J., Axinn, W. G., Cuijpers, P., Ebert, D. D., Green, J. G., ... & Kessler, R. C. (2016). Mental disorders among college students in the World Health Organization World Mental Health Surveys. *Psychological Medicine*, 46(14), 2955–2970. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0033291716001665>
- Corrigan, P. W. (2004). How stigma interferes with mental health care. *American Psychologist*, 59(7), 614–625. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0003-066X.59.7.614>
- Eisenberg, D., Hunt, J., & Speer, N. (2012). Help seeking for mental health on college campuses: Review of evidence and next steps for research and practice. *Harvard Review of Psychiatry*, 20(4), 222–232. <https://doi.org/10.3109/10673229.2012.712839>
- Gulliver, A., Griffiths, K. M., & Christensen, H. (2010). Perceived barriers and facilitators to mental health help-seeking in young people: A systematic review. *BMC Psychiatry*, 10(113). <https://doi.org/10.1186/1471-244X-10-113>
- Lui, J. C., Sagar-Ouriaghli, I., & Brown, J. S. L. (2022). Barriers and facilitators to help-seeking for common mental disorders among university students: A systematic review. *Journal of American College Health*. Advance online publication. <https://doi.org/10.1080/07448481.2022.2119859>
- Ma, K. K. Y., Anderson, J. K., & Burn, A. M. (2023). School-based mental health literacy interventions to promote help-seeking: A systematic review. *Child & Adolescent Mental Health*, 28(3), 408–424. <https://doi.org/10.1111/camh.12609>
- Martinez, A. B., Co, M., Lau, J., & Brown, J. S. L. (2020). Filipino help-seeking for mental health problems and associated barriers and facilitators: A systematic review. *Social Psychiatry and Psychiatric Epidemiology*, 55(11), 1397–1413. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00127-020-01937-2>

- O'Farrell, P., Wilson, C., & Shiel, G. (2022). Teachers' perceptions of the barriers to assessment of mental health in schools with implications for educational policy: A systematic review. *British Journal of Educational Psychology*, 93(1), 262–282. <https://doi.org/10.1111/bjep.12553>
- Priestley, M., Broglia, E., Hughes, G., et al. (2022). Student perspectives on improving mental health support services at university. *Counselling and Psychotherapy Research*. Advance online publication. <https://doi.org/10.1002/capr.12391>
- Republic Act No. 11036. (2018). An Act establishing a national mental health policy for the purpose of enhancing the delivery of integrated mental health services, promoting and protecting the rights of persons utilizing psychiatric, neurologic, and psychosocial health services, appropriating funds therefor, and other purposes. *Official Gazette*. Retrieved from <https://www.officialgazette.gov.ph/2018/06/20/republic-act-no-11036>
- Rickwood, D., Deane, F. P., Wilson, C. J., & Ciarrochi, J. (2005). Young people's help-seeking for mental health problems. *Australian e-Journal for the Advancement of Mental Health*, 4(3), 218–251. <https://doi.org/10.5172/jamh.4.3.218>
- Sue, D. W., & Sue, D. (2016). *Counseling the culturally diverse: Theory and practice* (8th ed.). Wiley.
- World Health Organization (2021). *Mental health atlas 2020*. World Health Organization. Retrieved from <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240036703>